

ELSEVIER

Online Link:- [click here](#)

Title:- Multiple Disease Prediction System Using Machine Learning

Authors: Bathnase Sainath ^{#1}, Singanaveni Rajesh ^{#2}, Dr.G.Madhukar sir(Assistant Professor) ^{#3}

#DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
CMR TECHNICAL CAMPUS
UGC AUTONOMOUS

Abstract — Data mining for healthcare is an interdisciplinary field of study that began in database statistics and is useful in examining the effectiveness of medical antidotes. Machine knowledge and data visualization Diabetes- related heart complaint is a kind of heart complaint that affects diabetics. Heart complaint, constantly known as cardiovascular complaint, refers to a set of conditions that affect the heart or blood vessels. Although various data mining type algorithms live for predicting heart complaint, there is shy data for predicting heart complaint in a diabetic existent. Because the decision tree model constantly beat the naive Bayes and support vector machine models, we OK- tuned it for the swish performance in reading the liability of heart complaint in diabetes individualities.

Keywords— data mining; healthcare sector, disease prediction

1. INTRODUCTION

The Multiple complaint vaticinator systems are substantially designed for the further colossal conditions like as Heart Disease, Cancer, etc. There-selected characteristics may occasionally not satisfy the changes in the complaint and its impacting factors which could lead to trip in results. As we live in a continuously evolving world, the symptoms of conditions also evolve over a course of time. Also, utmost of the current systems make the druggies stay for long ages by making them answer lengthy questionnaires. Machine literacy has been influential in chancing retired trends in large datasets in the world of medical wisdom. As we know, medical wisdom in the form of patient information and medical history generates huge quantities of databases. In this paper, we anatomized the different ways of Machine Learning strategies to probe and estimate different complaint gusted and cast grounded on time and database.

2. Working on Machine Learning

Machine Literacy is a subfield of artificial intelligence, which is astronomically defined as the capability of a machine to imitate intelligent mortal gets Artificial intelligence systems are used to perform complex tasks in a way that's analogous to how humans break problems

Fig.no 1: Working of Blockchain

2.1 Machine Learning features

Feature engineering is the pre-processing step of machine learning, which is used to transform

raw data into features that can be used for creating a predictive model using Machine learning or statistical Modelling. Feature engineering in machine learning aims to improve the performance of models. In this topic, we will understand the details about feature engineering in Machine learning.

The Machine Learning Process

Fig.no 2: Machine Learning features

Machine Literacy has come one of the most important technological advancements in recent times and has significantly impacted a broad range of diligence and operations.

Its main features are

- Prophetic modeling Data is used by machine literacy algorithms to produce models that read unborn events. These models can be used to determine the threat of a loan dereliction or the liability that a consumer would make a purchase, among other effects.
- robotization Machine learning algorithms automate the process of chancing patterns in data, taking lower mortal involvement and enabling more precise and effective analysis.
- Scalability Machine literacy ways are well suited for recycling big data because they're made to handle massive quantities of data. As a result, businesses can make opinions grounded on information picked from similar data.
- conception Algorithms for machine literacy are able of discovering broad patterns in data that can be used to dissect fresh, unexplored data. Indeed though the data used to train the model may not be incontinently applicable to the task at hand, they're useful for vaticinating unborn events.
- Adaptiveness As new data becomes available, machine literacy algorithms are erected to learn and acclimatize continuously. As a result, they can enhance their performance over time, getting

more precise and effective as further data is made available to them.

3. Literature survey

Over the years, many research teams have conducted several tests. The following are a few of the groups:

1. "Multi Disease Prediction Using Data Mining Techniques". In this study two different data mining classification techniques were used for the prediction of various diseases and their performance was compared to evaluate the best classifier. An important challenge in data mining and machine learning areas is to build precise and computationally efficient classifiers for Medical applications.
2. "Prediction of Heart Disease Using Machine Learning Algorithms". In this paper, two supervised data mining algorithm was applied to the dataset to predict the possibility of having heart disease of a patient and were analyzed with a classification model namely Naïve Bayes Classifier and Decision tree classification. The Decision tree model has predicted the heart disease patient with an accuracy level of 91% and the Naïve Bayes classifier has predicted heart disease patients with an accuracy level of 87%.
3. "Analysis of Heart Disease Prediction Using Datamining Techniques" Heart disease is one of the leading causes of death worldwide and the early prediction of heart disease is very important.
4. "Prediction of Cardiovascular Disease Using Machine Learning Algorithms". This paper contributes the correlative application and analysis of distinct machine learning algorithms in the R software which gives an immediate mechanism for the user to use the machine learning algorithms in R software for forecasting cardiovascular diseases.
5. "A Proposed Model for Lifestyle Disease Predict Using Support Machine

4. EXISTING SYSTEM

In the being system, the data set is generally small, for cases and conditions with specific conditions. The Multiple disease prediction systems are substantially designed for the further colossal conditions similar as Heart Disease, Cancer, etc. The pre-selected characteristics may occasionally not satisfy the changes in the complaint and its impacting factors which could lead to trip in results. As we live in a continuously evolving world, the symptoms of conditions also evolve over a course of time. Also, utmost of the current systems make the druggies stay for long ages by making them answer lengthy questionnaires.

5. PROPOSED SYSTEM

We are proposing such a system that will flaunt a simple and elegant User Interface and also be time efficient. To make it less time-consuming we are aiming at a more specific questionnaire which will be followed by the system. Our aim with this system is to be the connecting bridge between doctors and patients. The main feature will be machine learning, in which we will be using algorithms such as Naïve Bayes Algorithm, K-Nearest Algorithm, Decision Tree Algorithm, Random Forest Algorithm, and Support Vector Machine, which will help us in getting accurate predictions Also, will find which algorithm gives a faster and efficient result by comparatively-comparing. Another feature that our system will comprise is Doctor's Consultation. After delivering the results, our system will also suggest the user get a doctor's consultation on this report. By using this feature, we will not only address the other class of users i.e. the Doctors but we will also gain their trust in this system as in that this system is not affecting their business.

Support Vector Machine

Siddhardhan

Fig.no 3: Support vector machine

6. SYSTEM ARCHITECHTURE

Siddhardhan

Fig.no 4:Work Flow of Application

We built a multiple disease prediction system using machine learning in Python. We also deployed this web app using Stramlit. This multiple Diseases Prediction system uses ML that predicts diabetes, heart disease, and Parkinson's disease. Many of the existing machine learning models for health care analysis are concentrating on one disease per analysis. For example first is for liver analysis, one for cancer analysis, and one for lung diseases like that. If a user wants to predict more than one disease, he/she has to go through different sites. There is no common system where one analysis can perform more than one disease prediction. Some of the models have lower accuracy which can seriously affect patients' health. When an organization wants to analyze their patient's health reports, they have to deploy many models which in turn increases the cost as well as the time Some of the existing systems consider very few parameters which can yield false results.

Abstract Data mining for healthcare is an interdisciplinary field of study that originated in database statistics and is useful in examining the effectiveness of medical therapies. Machine learning and data visualization Diabetes-related heart disease is a kind of heart disease that affects diabetics. Diabetes is a chronic condition that occurs when the pancreas fails to produce enough insulin or when the body fails to properly use the insulin that is produced. Heart disease, often known as cardiovascular disease, refers to a set of conditions that affect the heart or blood vessels. Although various data mining classification algorithms exist for predicting heart disease, there is inadequate data for predicting heart disease in a diabetic individual. Because the decision tree model consistently beat the naive Bayes and support vector machine models, we fine-tuned it for the best performance in forecasting the likelihood of heart disease in diabetes individuals.

This web app was developed using Flask Web Framework and was deployed on the Heroku server. The models used to predict the diseases were trained on large Datasets. All the links for datasets and the Python notebooks used for model creation are mentioned below in this readme. The web app can predict the following Diseases:

Disease

- Diabetes
- Breast Cancer
- Heart Disease
- Kidney Disease
- Liver Disease

Models with their Accuracy of Prediction

Disease Type of Model Accuracy		
Diabetes	Machine Learning Model	98.25%
Breast Cancer	Machine Learning Model	98.25%
Heart Disease	Machine Learning Model	85.25%
Kidney Disease	Machine Learning Model	99%
Liver Disease	Machine Learning Model	78%

7. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This Technology improves the efficiency of detecting the disease by using Mathematical Algorithms and Machine Learning. This website provides a Quick test on Human Health and generates the report.

Assess with ease.

Fig.no:5 Home Page

RISK ASSESS Home About Us Help Login Sign Up

[YouTube Home](#)

About Multiple Disease Prediction

Welcome to Multiple Disease Prediction system !, a risk assessment system for medical institutions to generate risk assessments for their patients. RiskAssess started off as a company that formed strong relationships with medical institutions to help them generate their assessments with ease and maximum efficiency thus saving the organization's valuable time. Click below for Help.

[Help »](#)

Admin

Multiple Disease Prediction provides institutions with an Admin account to generate risk assessments for their patients.

[Login »](#)

How does it Work?

Multiple Disease Prediction makes use of machine learning models that helps generate accurate risk assessments.

[Generate Assessment »](#)

Terms & Conditions

If your organization has any concerns regarding the system please click below to read our Terms and Conditions.

[Terms & Conditions »](#)

© Multiple Disease Prediction. All Rights Reserved

Fig.no:6 About Us page

RiskAssess

Create Account

Username

Email

Password

[Sign Up](#)

Already have an account? [Login](#)

[Back Home](#)

Fig.no 7: Register Page

[YouTube Home](#)

RiskAssess

Account Login

Username

Password

remember me

[Login](#)

[Don't have an account? Sign Up](#)

[Back Home](#)

Fig.no 8: Login Page

RISK ASSESS

[Get Started](#)
[Disease Index](#)
[Breast Cancer](#)
[Diabetes](#)
[Heart Disease](#)
[Kidney Disease](#)
[Liver Disease](#)
[Logout](#)

Hello! Lets Get Started with RiskAssess

Welcome to RiskAssess!, a risk assessment system for medical institutions to generate risk assessments for their patients. RiskAssess started off as a company that formed strong relationships with medical institutions to help them generate their assessments with ease and maximum efficiency thus saving the organization's valuable time. Click below to learn about the diseases that RiskAssess is capable of assessing.

[Get Started »](#)

1. Cancer Prediction

Navigate to the "Cancer" section and add the corresponding details and click on predict to learn whether the patient is at the risk of this illness/disease.

2. Diabetes Prediction

Navigate to the "Diabetes" section and add the corresponding details and click on predict to learn whether the patient is at the risk of this illness/disease.

3. Heart Disease

Navigate to the "Heart Disease" section and add the corresponding details and click on predict to learn whether the patient is at the risk of this illness/disease.

4. Kidney Disease

Navigate to the "Kidney Disease" section and add the corresponding details and click on predict to

5. Liver Disease

Navigate to the "Liver Disease" section and add the corresponding details and click on predict to

6. Disease Index

Navigate to the "Disease Index" section and gain in-depth information about each of these

Fig.no:9 Dashboard page

RiskAssess - Disease Index

This is a directory of all the diseases that RiskAssess can generate assessments for, this index provides in depth details about the disease including its symptoms.

1. Breast Cancer

Breast cancer is cancer that develops from breast tissue. Signs of breast cancer may include a lump in the breast, a change in breast shape, dimpling of the skin, fluid coming from the nipple, a newly inverted nipple, or a red or scaly patch of skin.

Symptoms

Signs and symptoms of breast cancer may include:

Fig.no:10 Disease index

Breast Cancer Prediction

Please enter the patient details

Clump Thickness	<input type="text"/>
Uniform Cell size	<input type="text"/>
Uniform Cell shape	<input type="text"/>
Marginal Adhesion	<input type="text"/>
Single Epithelial Cell Size	<input type="text"/>
Rare Nuclei	<input type="text"/>

Fig.no: 11 Breast Cancer Prediction

Diabetes Prediction

Please enter the patient details

Number of Pregnancies	<input type="text" value="eg. 0 for male"/>
Glucose Level (mg/dL)	<input type="text" value="eg. 80"/>
Blood Pressure (mmHg)	<input type="text" value="eg. 80"/>
Skin Thickness (mm)	<input type="text" value="eg. 20"/>
Insulin Level (IU/mL)	<input type="text" value="eg. 80"/>

Fig.no:12 Diabetes Prediction

Heart Disease Prediction

Please enter the patient details

Age in Years	<input type="text" value="eg. 34"/>
Trest Bps	<input type="text" value="trestbps"/>
Cholesterol	<input type="text" value="chol"/>
Thalach	<input type="text" value="thalach"/>
Old Peak	<input type="text" value="oldpeak"/>
Sex_0	<input type="text" value="sex_0"/>

Fig.no:13 Heart Disease Prediction

Kidney Disease Prediction

Please enter the patient details

Blood Pressure	<input type="text" value="Blood Pressure"/>
Specific Gravity	<input type="text" value="Specific Gravity"/>
Albumin	<input type="text" value="Albumin"/>
Blood Sugar Level	<input type="text" value="Blood Sugar Level"/>
Red Blood Cells Count	<input type="text" value="Red Blood Cells Count"/>
Plac Cell Count	<input type="text" value="Plac Cell Count"/>

Fig.no:14 kidney Prediction

Liver Disease Prediction

Please enter the patient details

Total Bilirubin	<input type="text" value="Enter the Total Bilirubin"/>
Direct Bilirubin	<input type="text" value="Enter the Direct_Bilirubi"/>
Alkaline Phosphotase	<input type="text" value="Enter the Alkaline Phosq"/>
Alamine Aminotransferase	<input type="text" value="Enter the Alamine Amin"/>
Total Protiens	<input type="text" value="Enter the Total Protiens"/>
Alhumin	<input type="text" value="Enter the Alhumin"/>

Fig.no:15 Liver Disease Prediction

How to go about RiskAssess?

Please find below the Steps for Administrators to go about the Risk Assessment System. Click to [Learn More](#)

1. Log into the System using your account to start generating risk assessments

2. Select the type of disease for which you want to generate risks

3. Input the Patient's Vitals

4. Click on Submit

5. Get Assessment Result

6. Download as PDF

Fig.no:16 Help page

8. CONCLUSION

This paper gives a research of multiple pieces of research done in this field. Our Proposed System aims to bridge the gap between Doctors and Patients which will help both classes of users achieve their goals. This system provides support for multiple disease predictions using different Machine Learning algorithms. The present approach of many systems focuses only on automating this process which lacks in building the user's trust in the system. By providing Doctor's recommendations in our system, we ensure users' trust side by side ensuring that the Doctors will not feel that their Business is getting affected due to this System.

9. REFERENCES

- [1] Deepika Verma (Author), Dr. Nidhi Mishra (Author),” Analysis and Prediction of Breast cancer and Diabetes disease datasets using Data mining classification Techniques “978-1-5386-1959-9/17/\$31.00
- [2] Saba Bashir, Zain Sikander Khan, Farhan Hassan Khan, Aitzaz Anjum, Khurram Bashir "Improving Heart Disease Prediction Using Feature Selection Approaches" Proceedings of 2019 16th International Bhurban Conference on Applied Sciences & Technology (IBCAST) Islamabad, Pakistan, 8th – 12th January 2019.
- [3] Dhiraj Dahiwade, Prof. Gajanan Patel, Prof. Ektaa Meshram," Designing Disease Prediction Model Using Machine Learning Approach" 978-1-5386-7808-4/19/\$31.00
- [4] Prerna Jain, Amandeep Kaur " Big Data Analysis for Prediction of Coronary Artery Disease”
- [5] Dhiraj Dahiwade, Prof. Gajanan Patel, Prof. Ektaa Meshram "Designing Disease Prediction Model Using Machine Learning Approach”
- [6] Anjinkya Kunjir, Harshal Sawant, Nuzhat F.sheikh "Data Mining and Visualization for Prediction of Multiple Diseases in Healthcare”
- [7] Ayman Mir, Sudhir N. Dhage "Diabetes Disease Prediction using Machine Learning on Big Data of Healthcare”

Bathnase Sainath is currently pursuing B.Tech final year in the stream of Computer Science and Engineering in CMR Technical Campus, Medchal, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Singanaveni Rajesh is currently pursuing B.Tech final year in the stream of Computer Science and Engineering in CMR Technical Campus, Medchal, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

Mr. Dr. G. Madhukar is currently working as an Associate Professor in the department of Computer Science and Engineering, CMR Technical Campus, Medchal Hyderabad. he obtained his Doctorate degree Ph.d Sri Satya Sai University Of Technology & Medical Sciences, Sehore. His areas of specialization include machine learning and networks. He has 4 years of teaching Experience. He has published her research work in reputed journals with high impact factor.